

Studies on Synthesis and Antimicrobial Evaluation of some New Thiophenol Derivatives

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Keeping in view the medicinal importance of 4-thiazolidinones, α -aminonitriles and thiosemicarbazides, we have reported the synthesis of some new 4-thiazolidinone, α -amino nitrile and thiosemicarbazide derivatives of phenylthioacetyl hydrazine.

Thiophenol on reaction with ethyl chloroacetate and anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetone gave phenylthioethyl acetate, which was further treated with hydrazine hydrate to get phenylthioacetylhydrazine (1). Compound 1 when treated with aromatic aldehydes gave 1-(phenylthioacetyl)-2-substituted-benzalhydrazine (2), which on cycloaddition with mercaptoacetic acid in dioxane yielded 2-aryl-3-(phenylthioacetamido)-4-thiazolidinone (3). 4-(Aryl)-1-phenylthioacetyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (4) was obtained by the reaction of 1 and aryl isothiocyanates in boiling ethanol. Compound 1 easily underwent reaction with aromatic cyanohydrines obtained from aromatic aldehydes, KCN and acetic

acid to furnish α -(phenylthio acetylhydrazino)aryl acetonitrile (5) (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Backmann IR-30 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra ((CD₃)₂-CO) on a Jeol JNM-Fx-100 spectrometer.

Phenylthioacetylhydrazine (1): A mixture of thiophenol (1 mol, 110 g), ethyl chloroacetate (1 mol, 123 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.5 mol, 207 g) in acetone was refluxed on a water-bath under anhydrous conditions for 18 h. The excess of solvent was then distilled off, and the residue was dissolved in ethanol (95%), hydrazide hydrate added gradually and the contents were refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h, then cooled and poured over

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) K_2CO_3 , N_2H_4 , (ii) $ArCHO$, $EtOH$ (95%), (iii) 1,4-dioxan, $SHCH_2COOH$, (iv) $ArNCS$, $EtOH$ (95%) and (v) $ArCHO$, aq. KCN , $EtOH$ (95%).

crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised from rectified spirit (127 g, 70%), m.p. 63° (Found : C, 52.01 ; H, 4.85 ; N, 15.20 ; S, 17.40. $C_8H_{10}N_2OS$ requires : C, 52.75 ; H, 5.05 ; N, 15.38 ; S, 17.68%).

1-(Phenylthioacetyl)-2-benzalhydrazine¹ (2) : A mixture of phenylthioacetyl hydrazine (0.01 mol, 1.82 g) dissolved in ethanol (95%) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.06 g) was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. The excess of solvent was then distilled off, and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from rectified spirit (1.80 g, 67%), m.p. 128° (Found : C, 66.16 ; H, 4.99 ; N, 10.19 ; S, 11.67. $C_{15}H_{14}N_2OS$ requires : C, 66.66 ; H, 5.18 ; N, 10.37 ; S, 11.85%).

2-Phenyl-3-(phenylthioacetamido)-4-thiazolidinone² (3) : A mixture of 1-(phenylthioacetyl)-2-benzalhydrazine (0.005 mol, 1.35 g) dissolved in 1,4-dioxan (50 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol, 0.92 g) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 8 h. The contents were then cooled and poured into sodium bicarbonate solution (4 N). The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from rectified spirit, (1.20 g, 69%), m.p. 114° (Found : C, 58.90 ; H, 4.21 ; N, 8.00 ; S, 18.45. $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_2S_2$ requires : C, 59.3 ; H, 4.65 ; N, 8.13 ; S, 18.60%) ; ν_{max} 1 660 and 1 600 (C=O and amide group respectively), 1 430 (CH deformation of $-CH_2CO-$ group), 1 260,

1 250–1 100 (C–N linkage and 4-thiazolidinone ring system), 850–700 (mono- and disubstituted benzene ring), 3 180 and 2 860 cm^{-1} (secondary amino and CH_2) ; δ 7.72–7.25 (ArH), 3.61 (methylene), 3.74 (cyclic- CH_2), 2.98 (proton attached to nitrogen) and 4.17 (CH).

Similarly other compounds of the series were prepared.

4-(3'-Methylphenyl)-1-phenylthioacetyl-3-thiosemicarbazide³ (4) : A mixture of phenylthioacetylhydrazine (0.01 mol 1.82 g) and 3-methylphenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol 1.49 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. Excess of the solvent was then distilled off and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (2 g, 64%), m.p. 131° (Found : C, 57.75 ; H, 5.01 ; N, 12.48 ; S, 19.10. $C_{16}H_{17}N_3O_2S_2$ requires : C, 58.00 ; H, 5.14 ; N, 12.65 ; S, 19.33%) ; ν_{max} 1 700, 1 490 and 1 600 (C=O), 1 170 (C=S), 700 (C–S), 800, 745 and 750 (1,3-disubstituted and monosubstituted phenyl ring) and 1 285 cm^{-1} (C–N) ; δ 4.72 (NH of thiosemicarbazide), 2.67 (methylene), 5.03 (third –NH) and 7.25–7.34 (disubstituted phenyl ring).

Similarly other compounds of the series were prepared.

(+)- α -(Phenylthioacetylhydrazino)phenylacetone-trile⁴ (5) : A mixture of potassium cyanide (0.01

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3-5*

Compd. no.	Ar	M p. °C	Yield %
3a	C ₆ H ₅	128	67
b	2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	152	66
c	3OH.C ₆ H ₄	151	66
d	4OH.C ₆ H ₄	120	70
e	3,5-Br ₂ .2OH.C ₆ H ₃	134	68
f	4OH.3OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	164	63
g	5Br.4OH.3OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₂	178	61
h	4OH.5I.3OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₂	145	70
i	4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	116	63
j	3,4(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	192	64
k	3,4-(O.CH ₃ .O).C ₆ H ₃	161	64
l	4.Cl.C ₆ H ₃	157	66
m	3NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	133	63
n	4NO ₂ .CH	149	63
4a	C ₆ H ₅	125	63.09
b	2.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	120	63.44
c	3.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	131	64.95
d	4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	144	67.57
e	2.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	98	64.84
i	3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	132	66.28
g	4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	149	69.16
h	4.O.C ₆ H ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	131	70.63
i	2.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	140	65.43
j	3.Cl.C ₆ H ₃	135	62.58
k	4.Cl.C ₆ H ₃	164	69.70
l	4.Br.C ₆ H ₃	145	70.05
5a	C ₆ H ₅	128	67
b	2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	146	67
c	3.OH.C ₆ H ₄	144	67
d	4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	123	65
e	4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	176	64
f	5Br.4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₂	195	71
g	4OH.5I.3OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₂	202	68
h	4OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	150	64
i	3,4.(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	131	63
j	3,4.(O.CH ₃ .O).C ₆ H ₃	204	64
k	4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	172	67
l	4.Cl.C ₆ H ₃	156	66
m	3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	150	67
n	4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	147	67

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

mol, 0.65 g) dissolved in water (5 ml) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.06 g) was cooled upto 0°. To it glacial acetic acid (0.01 mol, 0.60 g) was added dropwise and the contents were kept at room temperature for 30 min. Phenylthioacetylhydrazine (0.01 mol, 1.82 g) dissolved in rectified spirit (5 ml) was then added and the contents were left overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with dilute HCl, dried and recrystallised from rectified spirit (2.01 g, 68%), m.p. 128°

(Found : C, 64.15 ; H, 4.89 ; N, 14.00 ; S, 10.59. C₁₆H₁₅N₃OS requires : C, 64.65 ; H, 5.05 ; N, 14.14 ; S, 10.77%) ; ν_{\max} 3 200 (secondary amino), 1 680 (secondary amide), 1 460 (C=O), 750 (mono-substituted phenyl ring), 3 100 (CH), 700 (C-S) and 2 200 cm⁻¹ (C≡N) ; δ 7.01-7.52 (ArH), 4.5 (NHNH) and 2.5 (CH).

Similarly other compounds of the series were prepared.

Biological activity: The compounds 3-5 were tested for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method⁵, using a species of gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*. The testing was carried out in 1,4-dioxane solution at a concentration of 100 μ g ml⁻¹. The standard drug sulphamethoxazole was used as control. The compounds exhibited moderate antibacterial activity.

In vitro antitubercular activity of compounds 3 and 4 was studied against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 10 and 100 μ g ml⁻¹. The retardation of growth was studied upto 6 weeks at 37°. The results are recorded in Table 1. The antitubercular activity was compared with standard INH. The experimental data has revealed low inhibitory effect.

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